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ECOLOGICAL DISTRIBUTION AND CONSERVATION SIGNIFICANCE OF TERRESTRIAL MOLLUSKS IN MOUNTAIN TURKISTAN

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ABSTRACT

The primary objective of this research is to investigate the distribution, anatomical and morphological characteristics of terrestrial mollusks inhabiting the Mountain Turkistan region, as well as to provide comprehensive information on their ecology, geographical distribution, limiting factors, and conservation strategies. The collection of research material was conducted in accordance with the methodology developed by A.A. Shileyko. Based on the findings of the study, it was determined that moisture availability plays a crucial role in the ecological requirements of mollusks. Accordingly, terrestrial mollusks can be classified into several ecological groups based on their moisture preferences, including hygrophilous, mesophilous, xerophilous, and mesoxerophilous species. The terrestrial mollusk species recorded in the Mountain Turkistan region are ecologically categorized primarily into hygrophilous, xerophilous, and mesoxerophilous groups. In order to ensure the conservation and effective monitoring of these species, it is essential to prioritize the protection of their natural habitats. In particular, measures should be taken to prevent deforestation and habitat degradation in areas where mollusks occur. Furthermore, the use of these habitats as grazing lands should be restricted, and further research focusing on habitat preferences and biological characteristics of terrestrial mollusks should be undertaken to prevent population decline and potential species extinction

Keywords: Arid, ecological, habitat, material, mesoxerophilic.

INTRODUCTION

Over the past several decades, increasing scientific attention has been directed toward the biological diversity of Uzbekistan, with particular emphasis on the Mountain Turkistan region (1–3). Numerous terrestrial mollusk species inhabiting this area have been significantly impacted by anthropogenic pressures, resulting in habitat degradation, fragmentation, and a decline in population sizes. As a consequence, some species have become locally extinct, while others are currently facing a high risk of extinction (4–6). In this context, the ecological and taxonomic investigation of terrestrial mollusks—particularly those species exhibiting either population stability or decline—has emerged as a critical research priority (7–9). Previous studies, including the monograph “*Terrestrial Mollusks of Uzbekistan and Adjacent Territories*,” provide comprehensive anatomical and morphological analyses of more than 170 terrestrial mollusk species, along with detailed insights into their evolutionary history (10–12). However, these works offer limited information regarding species that are currently thriving or experiencing population declines (13–15). According to the second volume of the *Red Book of the Republic of Uzbekistan*, 184 animal species are classified as threatened with extinction, of which 14 belong to the phylum Mollusca. Notably, only two of these listed species are terrestrial mollusks (16–18). Despite the fact that the Mountain Turkistan region harbors a substantial proportion of the terrestrial mollusk species vulnerable to extinction, comprehensive and detailed data on their current status, distribution, and ecological requirements remain insufficient (19–21).

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Malacological methods developed by Shileyko (1978) were primarily employed for the preparation, cleaning, and examination of mollusk specimens. The present study is based on terrestrial mollusks collected from various regions of Uzbekistan during the period from 2021 to 2025 (Map 1).

The results of this research contribute to a better understanding of mollusk adaptation to changing environmental conditions and enable predictions regarding the impact of anthropogenic activities on their habitats. Furthermore, the findings provide a scientific basis for the development and implementation of conservation measures aimed at preserving terrestrial mollusk species.

Map (1): Location map. Collection points for material. *Candaharia (Levanderia) langarika*-40°14'43.85"N, 67° 03'36.34"E, *Pseudonapaeus (Pseudonapaeus) sinistrorsa*-38°02'25.07" N, 67°15'04.52"E, *Pseudonapaeus (Pseudonapaeus) shahristanikus* 39°36'48.1"N 68°26'58.3"E, *Leucozonella (Leucozonella) schileykoi*-38°14'16.53" N, 67°10'52.05"E

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Cochlicopa (Cochlicopa) starobogatovi (Pazilov et Azimov, 2003).

Ten specimens were collected from the Turkistan ridge. The shell of is characterized by a monomorphic structure. Its whorls are clockwise coiled, with one whorl detached and slightly tilted towards the mouth. The shell colour is ochre-yellowish and is distinct from other species belonging to this group. The shell resembles a small snail, with its sculpture formed by delicate ribs. The aperture of shell is elongated and palatal, with a single parietal callus. Its margins are unflanged, except for one that is slightly thickened. The height of shell ranges from 6.9 to 7.4 mm, with a large diameter ranging from 2.5 to 3.1 mm.

Habitat. Fragile, naturally rare.

Distribution: Found in the Turkistan canal system.

Habitat. Inhabits biotopes with diverse vegetation among various grasses in the foothills.

Population. Finally, a small number of 10 individuals per square meter or 1 or 2 individuals are possible.

Lifestyle. Undocumented. Threatening factors. Their population is declining due to anthropogenic influences.

Conservation measures. Understanding their habitats, numbers, and lifestyle is essential for comprehensive conservation efforts.

Leucozonella (Leucozonella) schileykoi (Pazilov et Daminova, 2001).

DESCRIPTION

The shell is depressed and strongly compressed dorsoventrally, with a conical embryonic portion. The height of the aperture is approximately equal to the shell height. The shell consists of 5–5.5 moderately expanding whorls. The last whorl is relatively broader, exceeding the shell axis by approximately 1.5 turns, and the aperture is slightly deflected laterally. The shell coloration is ochre-yellowish, with a distinctly exposed and sharply defined embryonic portion. The peripheral groove is weakly expressed. Shell sculpture is characterized by fine spiral striations.

The aperture is elongated and lip-like; its margins are closely approximated at the point of attachment and connected by delicate ridges. The peristome is thin, and the labial sinus is poorly developed. The columellar margin is slightly twisted. Shell height ranges from 7.5 to 9.5 mm, with a major diameter of 13.5–15.5 mm and a minor diameter of 12.0–13.2 mm.

Habitat. A naturally rare species with a localized distribution.

Distribution. Turkistan canal system.

Microhabitat. Occurs in foothill and piedmont zones, inhabiting areas beneath stones and among rocky debris.

Population status. Previously common; however, population numbers have markedly declined over the past two decades.

Biology and lifestyle. Insufficiently studied.

Threatening factors. Habitat destruction associated with land development, settlement expansion, and the use of natural substrates as construction materials.

Conservation measures. Protection of remaining natural landscapes and targeted studies of the species' biology and ecological requirements are strongly recommended.

Pseudonapaeus (Pseudonapaeus) shahristanikus (Pazilov et Azimov, 2003). Material collected from 15 specimens from the Turkistan ridge. The shell of it is oval-cylindrical, depressed. It consists of 6 whorls, coiled tightly, connected to each other through shallow sutures. The final whorl is characterized by a sharp increase towards the aperture, forming $3/2$ of the height of the shell. The shell exhibits a uniform, ochre-yellowish color, with various degrees of development in the spiral sculpture, shiny and glossy. Its sculpture is composed of fine, unbroken grooves. The aperture of the shell is lip-like, slightly tilted, with its attaching point not close to each other, its edges

slightly thickened, attached with a parietal callus. The height of the shell ranges from 6 to 7 mm, with a large diameter of 3 to 3.5 mm.

Habitat. It is disappearing.

Distribution. Currently only found in the Turkiston canal system.

Living place. It inhabits areas at an altitude of 2500-2800 meters, living on large limestone rocks.

Number. Sharply declining.

Lifestyle. Undocumented.

Threatening factors. The destruction of habitats by limestone mining and the elimination of habitats as a result of quarrying.

Conservation measures. Understanding the habitats, numbers, and lifestyles comprehensively and establishing protection in their habitats.

Pseudonapaeus (Pseudonapaeus) sinistrorsa (Pazilov, 2004).

Material examined. A total of 17 specimens were collected from the Turkistan Ridge.

Description. The shells are sinistral (left-coiled), moderately conical in shape, with a slightly depressed apex. They consist of 5.5–6 tightly coiled whorls connected by shallow sutures. The final whorl is oriented toward the aperture. Shell coloration is dull yellow. The shell sculpture is characterized by fine grooves formed by axial ribs. The aperture is oval, slightly thickened, with raised margins. The parietal region of the aperture is not tightly closed and is connected by a smooth callus. Shell height ranges from 10.0 to 12.5 mm, while the major diameter measures 4.0–5.0 mm.

Habitat. A disappearing species.

Distribution. Restricted to the northeastern part of the Turkistan canal system.

Microhabitat. *Pseudonapaeus sinistrorsa* inhabits elevations of approximately 2,500 m above sea level, occurring on various limestone substrates and within vegetation associated with limestone outcrops.

Population status. Rapidly declining.

Biology and lifestyle. Insufficiently documented.

Threatening factors. Habitat destruction resulting from limestone mining and quarrying activities.

Conservation measures. Comprehensive investigations of habitat conditions, population size, and biological characteristics are required, along with the establishment of protected areas within the species' range.

Preservation measures. Conservation of natural landscapes within the species' habitats and further studies of its biology are essential. Based on the data obtained, the four species discussed above are currently classified as endangered. The research

findings indicate that naturally stable species account for 25%, gradually declining species comprise 50%, and extinct species represent 25% of the total.

According to the classification proposed by A. Pazilov and J. Azimov, terrestrial gastropods occurring in Uzbekistan and adjacent regions are divided into four zoogeographical groups: East Asian, Trans-Altaic, Central Asian, and Ancient Asian species. From a zoogeographical perspective, all terrestrial mollusk species recorded in Uzbekistan belong to the Central Asian endemic complex and are considered autochthonous in origin (22–25).

The range of autochthonous species is delimited by the Central Asian mountainous regions, and it is estimated that they emerged within the region during the late Pleistocene or the end of the Pliocene, independently from the European-Caucasian Hygromiidae and Euamphaliinae families, with which representative(s) of the Trichiinae might have been associated.

Uzbekistan is home to a number of species that are abundant as well as species that are scarce, and these species differ from one another in terms of their ecological characteristics. For example, *Cochlicopa starobogatovi* are considered hygrophilic species, living in humid habitats. While *L. schieykoi*, *Ps.shahristanicus*, and *Ps.sinistrorsa* are mesoxerophilic species. Species that are abundant and those that are scarce have not been distributed uniformly across altitude zones. For instance, *S.starobogatovi* and *L. schieykoi* are found only in the foothill region, *Ps.shahristanicus* are found exclusively in mountainous regions. Fig. 3

Figure 2. Ecology and altitudinal distribution of rare and endangered land mollusk species

Until the 1990s, during the period of the former Soviet Union, large-scale agricultural and industrial projects were implemented with limited consideration of their environmental and social impacts, resulting in substantial disruption to the natural biodiversity of Uzbekistan. The expansion of cotton monoculture, large-scale land reclamation for irrigation, and the degradation of unique biological communities in affected areas led to the decline and local extinction of several species, ultimately causing a general reduction in the populations of native fauna (26–28).

Agricultural settlements, which form the foundation of irrigation-based farming systems in Uzbekistan, were extensively developed in foothill regions to expand arable land. Consequently, ecological conditions in these areas underwent significant alterations. As a result, populations of terrestrial mollusk species that were poorly adapted to such transformed environments declined sharply, with some species disappearing entirely. For instance, *S. starobogatovi* and *L. schileykoi*, which were considered common species 20–30 years ago with population densities of 3–5 individuals per m², are currently encountered at densities of only one individual per 10–15 m².

Furthermore, the rapid expansion of the textile industry, deforestation, and the excessive use of highland pastures beyond their sustainable capacity have contributed to the destruction of ecologically valuable habitats. The intensification of recreational activities has further exacerbated habitat degradation, leading to the loss of local mountain ecotourism environments. For example, continuous grazing by mountain goats has resulted in the disappearance of habitats occupied by *Leucozonella schileykoi* (29–31).

To conserve and restore populations of rare and declining mollusk species in Uzbekistan, it is essential to prioritize the protection of their habitats. This includes significantly reducing deforestation of trees and shrubs in areas inhabited by mollusks, limiting overgrazing in mountainous regions, and regulating the use of pastures to prevent further degradation. Additionally, comprehensive studies of mollusk habitat requirements and biological characteristics are necessary to develop effective conservation strategies and to prevent further species loss.

CONCLUSION

In the Mountain Turkistan region, seven rare and declining terrestrial mollusk species have been recorded, representing five genera and three families.

According to the threat categories of the *Red Book of the Republic of Uzbekistan*, these rare and declining species can be classified into three conservation categories based on their risk of extinction. The category of **naturally rare species** includes *Cochlicopa starobogatovi*; **threatened species** include *Pseudonapaeus zerafschanicus*; and the **endangered species** category comprises *Leucozonella schileykoi*, *Pseudonapaeus shahristanikus*, and *Pseudonapaeus sinistrorsa*.

From an ecological perspective, the rare and declining terrestrial mollusks of Mountain Turkistan are grouped into hygrophilous, xerophilous, and mesoxerophilous types.

The primary factors contributing to the rarity and decline of these species in Mountain Turkistan are predominantly anthropogenic. Foremost among these is the lack of effective protection of their habitats, including extensive deforestation of trees

and shrubs in areas inhabited by mollusks. Additionally, the excessive use of these habitats as pasturelands beyond their sustainable capacity has resulted in overgrazing, leading to habitat degradation and subsequent population decline.

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